

A SOCIOLOGICAL APPROACH TO THE POLITICAL COMPETENCE OF THE LEADER

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***Abstract.** Today's leader must have the necessary competence for his work. What is competence? Competence is an ability formed in every manager based on acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications. Managers and employees who speak different languages and have their own dialects work in all areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

***Key words:** political competence, sociolinguistics, approach.*

There is a need for a leader participating in political processes to speak freely in the accepted state language, without resorting to any dialect or dialect. This issue, first of all, is important in preventing the emergence of negative perceptions or misconceptions about the territorial and social origin of the leader in employees or citizens, and secondly, in the correct formation of political competence.

In order to carry out daily activities in a multinational society, people need to have sociolinguistic knowledge in order to communicate.

Today, the problem of leadership competence is considered urgent for any other country. The development of the country, its political and economic well-being, as well as the effectiveness of public administration largely depend on the effective management decisions of public service representatives.

The concept of political competence is significantly manifested in identifying and solving shortcomings in the public administration system. In the concept of administrative reforms of every country, rational management of the state is one of the foundations of the successful development of the socio-economic sphere of the country [1].

The political competence of the leader is expressed differently in political strategy and political tactics. [4].

"Strategy" means a long-term plan for achieving fundamental goals aimed at the development of the social sphere.

The question of competence is very important in the political strategy, and it applies to civil servants who hold high positions in the state administration apparatus. Because they are the main people who determine the political direction of the state and the social life of citizens. Of course, such leaders are qualified with professional knowledge of the country's political and economic life

assistants and advisors are available. But the main weight in decision-making always remains with the leader, who is responsible for the management decisions made.

A politically competent leader is a person who has not only theoretical knowledge, ability to think creatively, but also the ability to set real tasks and implement them consistently, taking into account the current needs of the population [3].

There are several stages of the activity of a politically competent leader, in which the strategic competence of the leader is manifested:

The first step is to define the main social goals. This stage is characterized by the realization of the role of the leader in the development of his country and how he can influence the development of society. After that, a clear, achievable, non-contradictory socio-political goal is set.

The second stage is the choice of a model of social development. At this stage, the big leader analyzes the positive and negative aspects of his country and chooses

the most suitable model. It can be a completely new model created on the basis of experiences in the political and economic spheres, or a model taken from other countries. If the model does not sufficiently match the country's capabilities, then the next stage of the leader's political competence is to correct or completely abandon such a model.

The third stage is competence in the field of geopolitical interests. Geopolitical interests are defined as interests arising from the geographical location of states and the advantages and disadvantages associated with them. Geopolitical competence is an understanding of the relationship between the economic, political, military, informational power of the state and its geographical location, distinguishing links connecting geography and strategy, as a result of which geostrategy appears.

Choosing and applying the best tactical solution for a leader is focused on a specific position. At this stage, it is important that the leader does not lose his position and defends his position. Tactically sound leaders are who have the ability to communicate with different segments of the population, as well as are aware of skilled tactics as a control of the situation. It is very difficult to achieve political competence for civil servants holding high positions. The reason for this is that such leaders must be competent in considering and taking into account the opinions of the population, take into account the various interests of civil servants, and also eliminate disagreements between society and civil service representatives with the help of competent management decisions. [3].

Changes are taking place in the political, economic and social spheres in the modern world. In this regard, it is not possible to process the material obtained on the basis of the experience of state administration in higher educational institutions and other educational institutions aimed at training and improving the qualifications of people who want to work in state bodies and include it in the curriculum.

Existing curricula mainly focus on stable situations in the country and around the world, and pay little attention to crises and emergencies [2].

The passivity of educational structures cannot be justified by the lack of modern knowledge of the management system among civil servants. In order to improve political skills and professionalism, they can use horizontal connections within the existing system between representatives of the civil service. The solution to this problem can be the creation of a distance education system, the focus of which is mainly on the development of self-organization. Existing approaches allow civil service employees to develop creative thinking, innovative management decision-making skills, and learn the most effective ways to communicate with colleagues. Constant communication, learning and assimilation of knowledge from other people working in the same field allows you to constantly improve your skills. It is in this respect that there are several types of approaches to the political competence of the leader, one of which is the sociolinguistic approach. Sociolinguistics (sociological linguistics) is a branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between language and the social conditions of its existence. Sociolinguistics is closely related to linguistic disciplines such as psycholinguistics and ethno-linguistics. The sociolinguistic approach was developed by U. Labov and his followers since 1972 (Labov 1972; Chambers, Trudgill 1980; Trudgill 1986). The basis of the sociolinguistic approach is that all language changes occur and are transmitted through specific people united in social groups. Language changes spread because people not only change their own speech, but also adopt and copy other people's speech and transmit their linguistic features to others. In this case, the change of dialect boundaries is interpreted as a movement in space (a certain place, territory) and the interaction of specific people. Dialect, dialects are spread not only in a certain region, but also in certain social strata. Different social groups have different linguistic phenomena. People living in the same area may speak several varieties of the same language. Therefore, language, as a part of social life, affects not only the laws of language itself, but also changes in social life. This requires the leader's attitude towards this language and the ability to effectively use it in managing people.

Sociolinguistic research makes it possible to determine to what extent the linguistic features of a certain area depend on the social structure of society and how such a structure contributes to or hinders the processes of linguistic change.

The process of language change is always socially distributed, that is, any innovation spreads through social strata at different speeds. The leading leaders of language changes are usually representatives of the middle strata of society. Usually, the lowest and highest layers of society do not act as initiators and leaders of language changes. Social groups of people the main reason that encourages the adoption and copying of new formations that contribute to the spread of innovations is the reputation of a certain social group. A study of language changes in Norwich, Great Britain, led to conclusions about the existence of covert and overt prestige among leaders or people.

Implicit prestige is characteristic of the lower strata of society, whose adherence to old or dialectal forms prevents innovation (language change) from entering their environment. Such language innovations, although perceived as "more correct", are usually associated with layers of society whose values do not serve as a guide for such groups.

An indicator of the existence of implicit reputation is the situation where working-class people usually characterize their speech behavior as more "wrong" than it really is.

Open reputation is characteristic of situations in which native speakers describe their speech behavior as more "correct" in relation to the actual situation. This indicates that they want to speak their own language, dialect, dialect or dialect and intuitively increase the frequency of occurrence of the linguistic phenomenon that serves as an object of imitation in their mind.

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